

**TREND OF MACRO ECONOMIC VARIABLE ESPECIALLY ON
DOMESTIC SAVINGS AND DOMESTIC EXPENDITURE, NATIONAL
SAVING AND ITS IMPACT ON ECONOMY OF A COUNTRY: A CASE OF
SRI LANKA**

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Abstract: *This paper analyses the pattern of domestic saving, domestic expenditure during last fifteen years and the impact of these two variables on gross domestic product of Sri Lanka for the same period. Saving is the macroeconomic variable which is not only contributes to the investment but to control the general price level of an economy but too much of saving in a given year of a Country will impact on the economy by negatively. That is, it reduces the purchasing power of the people in a given year and slowdown the business hence demand for business loans falls. On the other hand if saving falls in a given year then the purchasing power of the people of the Country will increase which also impact the economy negatively. That is, the general price level of the Country will increase hence level of inflation will increase. So, the policy makers of the Country focus on a policy carefully to balance the saving and expenditure in a given year. The study further reveals that there should be focused on Gross Domestic Expenditure and National Saving since these two variables impact on Gross Domestic Product positively. Gross Domestic saving and Unemployment Rate are not significant and have negative impact on the GDP since the p value of the Domestic Saving and Unemployment Rate are more than p values (>0.005). As such, a proper mechanism or a way to be set up to increase the private consumption and the government investment without affecting the component of National Saving such as domestic saving and attracting foreign investment as saving of the government to economic growth of Sri Lanka in the next years.*

Key Word: *Domestic Saving, National Saving, Domestic Expenditure, GDP, and Unemployment Rate*

Introduction

Domestic saving is one of the macro-economic factors contributing economic growth of a country. Saving is the function of disposable income of a family. If disposable income of a family increases, the saving also will increase. Economic theory explains the relationship between the Saving (S) and disposable Income (Y_d) as $S = -a + b \cdot Y_d$. In developing countries, the saving is less due to low income of the families. The developing countries which are struggle in increasing savings focus on attracting foreign direct investments. One research revealed that national saving of Sri Lanka had been increased from 15 percent of GDP in 1970 to 25 percent of GDP in 2010 and the rise in national saving was fundamentally fueled and sustained by the

private sector [1]. Total national savings (S) equal the Private savings plus Government savings. Private savings consists of Y, T and C where Y is the Income, T is the tax paid by the private peoples and C is the consumption of the private peoples. That is, $S_p = Y - T - C$. In the meantime, the Government saving consists of T and G where T is total tax revenue of the government and G is total government expenditure. That is, $S_g = T - G$ [2]. Too much of saving is considered in reducing purchasing power of the family in short term. That is, if increasing domestic savings of a developing country will helps in reducing dependence on foreign financing and it provides long term financing base for investments. Many studies have established a favorable association between an increase in aggregate savings and a country's economic development. Previous experience has demonstrated that low savings rates result in budget and balance of payments deficits (Ribaj, A., Mexhuani, F.2021).Some economics pointed out that too much of saving from the total income of a Country also contributes in reducing the ability of purchasing power of the Country. As a result, based on theory, business will drop drastically and it will impact on the economy of the Country negatively.

Economic growth means an increasing value of the GDP of a given Country in a given year with comparing the value of the GDP of the previous year. Economic growth of Sri Lanka has been seen decreasing since start of COVID 19 occurred all over the world. On the other hand, Domestic Expenditure also impacts on the Gross Domestic Product (GDP). GDE is made up of consumption and investment. Consumption expenditure is divided into two categories: private consumption and government consumption, which includes general government spending on activities such as defense, public services, and social protection. Consumption expenditure, which accounted for 81.1 percent of total economic expenditure at current prices in 2020, grew at a slower pace of 2.1 percent during the year, compared to 7.4 percent growth in 2019, hampered by lockdowns and cautious consumer spending due to income uncertainty.

Investment is measured in the form of gross fixed capital formation defined as acquisition of produced assets minus disposal of a given year. That is, investment on Construction, Transport Equipment, Machinery and equipment, information, communication Technology equipment and intellectual property product is measured based on gross fixed capital formation of a County in a given year. Investment spending at current prices fell by 6.2 percent in 2020, compared to 5.5 percent in 2019, owing mostly to uncertainty about the pandemic's recovery duration, both locally and worldwide [2].

Gross Domestic Product (GDP) is assessed using three approaches: the production approach, the spending approach, and the income method. Income approach not only in Sri Lanka but in all over the world but for the research purpose,

production approach is considered. The general components of GDP measured in production approach are listed as Agriculture, Forestry & Fishing, Industries and Services. All growing of agriculture, forestry & fishing in the Island of Sri Lanka is measured at the constant price based on the price of year 2015 [3]. Likewise other two sectors such as Industries & Services produced in a given year in the Island of Sri Lanka are measured at a constant price based on the price of year 2015. Adding these all three sectors in a given year is the total price of all production of the Island of Sri Lanka in a given year at a constant price based on the price of year 2015 [4].

Expansion of a Production Possibilities Curve of a Country is the way of explaining economic growth of a given Country. The expansion is not merely happened without finding a new resource or finding advanced technology in the production process. The government elected from time to time introduces some mechanisms or macroeconomic policies to expand the existing resource or the way of production by using modern technologies [5]. As such, some new things have been introduced in many sectors of the business of Sri Lanka to increase the volume of the output in a given year from last ten years such as In the year 2022, the National Institute of Fundamental Studies (NIFS) developed a policy for technology transfer to ease the use of technology and research in local manufacturing businesses, several programs were introduced for the expeditious adoption of sustainable agriculture protection, while encouraging local production of organic fertilizer, including a provision of an incentive of Rs. 12500.00 per hectare, to farmers who produce organic fertilizer for their own paddy cultivation in the 2021/2022 Maha season, Adoption of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) to increase the knowledge of the information and communication among private and the government sector's employees to do the business in an innovative method but the use of the ICT in the government sector is not in par with the private sector [6].

Objective:

To carry out the research on domestic savings, domestic expenditure and how these historical data impact on the historical data of GDP of Sri Lanka for last fifteen years including the period affected by COVID 19.

Methodology

The paper analyzes mix method of qualitative and quantitative of secondary data of Domestic Saving, National Saving, Unemployment Rate and Domestic Expenditure and the GDP of Sri Lanka collected from the report of Central Bank of Sri Lanka for last 15 years. The collected data were put into SPSS statistical tool to analyze the impact of these independent variables of Gross Domestic Saving, Gross Domestic Expenditures, Inflation and Interest Rate on dependent variable of GDP of the Country.

Results and discussions

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R, R square, adjusted R square and standard error of the estimation mentioned below are very important to predict the correlation of Domestic Expenditure, Domestic Saving, National Saving and Rate of Unemployment with dependent variable of Gross Domestic Product at Market Value. R, R square and adjusted R square are equal to one which is perfect correlation between independent variables and dependent variables. That is, independent variable such as domestic Expenditure, Domestic Saving, National Saving and Rate of Unemployment are totally influenced by the dependent variable of Gross Domestic Product of Sri Lanka for last 15 years. Furthermore, the F ratio in the ANOVA table determines if the overall regression model fits the data well. According to the table, the independent factors statistically predict the dependent variable. That is, F (4, 32.393), P0.005 suggests that the regression model fits the data well.

Table 1. sum of square and mean value.

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	404341512686523.800	4	101085378171630.950	20726.921	.000 ^b
Residual	48770089339.950	10	4877008933.995		
Total	404390282775863.750	14			

a. Dependent Variable: GDP_Market_Price

b. Predictors: (Constant), Unemployment Rate, Gross Domestic Expenditure, National Saving, Gross Domestic Saving

Further analyzing, the coefficient table shows that unstandardized coefficients, t value and p value (Sig). from this table the regression model for the independent variable such as Domestic Expenditure, Domestic Saving, National Saving and Unemployment rate with dependent variable of Gross Domestic Product (GDP) is expressed in an equation as below.

$$\text{GDP (at Market Price)} = -242771.853 + 1.080 (\text{GDE}) - .097 (\text{GDS}) + 1.021 (\text{NS}) - 53214.735 (\text{UR}) \text{ where}$$

GDP = Gross Domestic Product, GDE = Gross Domestic Expenditure, GDS = Gross Domestic Saving, NS = National Saving and UR = Unemployment Rate

Table 2. Coefficient of variation

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	-242771.853	242292.941		-1.002	.340
Gross Domestic Expenditure	1.080	.051	.759	21.383	.000
Gross Domestic Saving	-.097	.034	-.085	-2.896	.016
National Saving	1.021	.034	.341	30.239	.000
Unemployment Rate	-53214.735	67303.903	-.005	-.791	.447

a. Dependent Variable: GDP_Market_Price

The above multiple regression equation reveals that, all other things are constant, if GDE increase one million rupees, the GDP is increased by 1.080 million in a given year but if GDS increase by 1 million rupees, the GDP is fallen by 0.097 million in a given year. Likewise, the NS increased by 1 million, the GDP will be increased by 1.021 million. But, by looking the above table, the p value (sig.) of GDE and NS are 0.000 and 0.000 respectively. The p value of the two variables shows that there is a significant association between the independent factors and the dependent variable since the p values of the two variables are less than 0.005 ($p < 0.005$), whereas the p values of GDS and Unemployment Rate are greater than 0.005, that is, the p value of GDS and Unemployment Rate are 0.016 and 0.447 respectively which is insignificant to do the prediction.

Conclusion

The study reveals that there should be focused on Gross Domestic Expenditure and National Saving since these two variables impact on Gross Domestic Product positively. As such, a proper mechanism or a way to be set up to increase the private consumption and the government investment without affecting the component of National Saving such as domestic saving and attracting foreign investment as saving of the government to economic growth of Sri Lanka in the next years.

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